

The value of low- and negative-carbon fuels in the transition to net-zero emission economies: lifecycle greenhouse gas emissions and cost assessments across multiple fuel types

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Highlights:

- 16 lifecycle pathways for low- or negative-carbon H₂, liquid fuel, and synthetic natural gas production from biomass, electricity, and natural gas feedstocks are analyzed.
- Hydrogen pathways are less costly to decarbonize than liquid fuel and synthetic gas pathways for the same input feedstock.
- Gasification-based production from biomass coupled with carbon capture and storage is particularly attractive in the presence of carbon emission prices.

Abstract:

In recent macro-energy systems modeling studies of net-zero emissions pathways for the United States and elsewhere, fuels made via gasification of sustainably produced biomass coupled with carbon capture and storage (CCS) play critical roles in achieving economy-wide net-zero greenhouse gas emissions because they provide carbon-negative energy carriers. In this study, we develop lifecycle greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and cost assessments to provide insights into the environmental and economic cost and value of hydrogen (H₂), synthetic natural gas (SNG), and Fischer-Tropsch liquid (FTL) fuels made from 1) biomass, coupled with CCS, 2) natural gas, with CCS, and 3) renewably-generated electricity. We find that H₂ production pathways are less costly to decarbonize than FTL and SNG pathways that use the same input feedstock and also provide the largest reductions in lifecycle GHG emissions per unit of delivered fuel. Sensitivity analyses on the levelized costs of carbon mitigation (LCCM) indicate that capital costs and capacity factors are influential for most of the pathways. Costs for processes that use natural gas

as feedstock are more sensitive to changes in input feedstock intensity than other processes. Finally, we find that fuel production pathways starting from biomass and including CCS have the highest carbon mitigation potentials among all feedstock pathways. They also have the lowest production costs beyond certain threshold carbon emission price levels. Our findings help explain the critical role that biomass-based hydrogen production with CCS plays in macro-energy system models of the U.S. transition to net-zero emissions.

Key Words: Biomass; Biofuels; Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS); Hydrogen; Fischer-Tropsch liquid; Synthetic natural gas

1. Introduction

Many countries have announced aims to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2050 [1, 2], as needed to meet goals of the Paris agreement to keep the global temperature increase to well below 2 °C and ideally below 1.5 °C relative to the preindustrial level. Net-zero refers to a balance between the amount of GHGs emitted and removed from the atmosphere annually due to human activities [3]. Achieving this balance requires significant reductions in emissions across all economic sectors, as well as the removal of some GHGs via natural solutions (e.g., afforestation) and via negative emissions technologies like bioenergy with carbon capture and storage and direct air capture of CO₂ [4].

Although electrification of end uses coupled with decarbonization of the power sector is widely regarded as a linchpin for achieving net-zero economies, it is difficult for a society to function on electricity alone as a final energy carrier [5]. As such, low- or negative-carbon fuels (herein referred to as clean fuels), such as hydrogen (H₂), Fischer-Tropsch liquids (FTL), and/or synthetic natural gas (SNG), are expected to have broad ranges of applications in future net-zero economies. Many previous studies suggest H₂ may play a critical role in achieving net-zero emissions economies [6, 7]. It can replace fossil fuels in power generation and chemicals production, be blended into pipeline gas to help decarbonize the natural gas sector, and decarbonize sectors that are difficult to electrify such as long-distance heavy-duty trucks and heavy industry (e.g., steel production) [7-9]. Similarly, biomass-derived or other low- or negative-carbon synthetic liquid fuels can substitute for fossil-derived liquid fuels in difficult-to-electrify transportation applications, such as heavy-duty trucks, trains, and planes [10, 11].

Likewise, clean SNG can be used to help decarbonize industries where the direct use of electricity is difficult and thermal power plants are not equipped with CO₂ capture [12].

Macro-energy system modeling studies project prominent roles for clean fuels in national transitions to net-zero emissions. Williams *et al.* [13] investigated multiple scenarios for the United States to achieve net-zero carbon emissions by 2050. They found around 50% of final energy demand was met with fuels (i.e., hydrocarbons and H₂) in a least-cost carbon-neutral pathway, and low-carbon fuels, such as those that are the focus here, replaced most or all fossil fuels. In a more-comprehensive and detailed modeling study for the United States, Larson, *et al.* [14], constructed five plausible technological pathways for the country to achieve net-zero GHG emissions economy-wide by 2050. While electrification plays a large role in all five pathways, liquid and gaseous fuels still account for 40% to 55% of all final energy use in 2050 when economy-wide net-zero emissions are achieved. H₂ made via biomass gasification with CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) and FTL synthesized from clean H₂ and CO₂ are the most important low-carbon/carbon-negative fuels across the five pathways, while clean SNG (and bio-electricity) play lesser roles. In Larson, *et al.* [14], the potential U.S. biomass feedstock supply achievable without land-use changes is estimated to be about 13 EJ/y (0.7 billion t/yr dry biomass) in 2050, based on the US Department of Energy's county-by-county analysis of potentially available feedstocks [15]. In [14] approximately 2/3 of the potential feedstocks are classified as residues of annual agricultural activities or grasses grown on land currently not used for agriculture. The remaining 1/3 are sustainable-forestry residues, which are also amenable to processing via technological routes that will be analyzed in this paper.

Currently in the U.S., most H₂ is produced by natural gas reforming (without CO₂ capture), and most liquid and gaseous fuels are of fossil origin, with inherent and significant life cycle GHG emissions. Various studies have analyzed pathways for producing lower-carbon versions of the aforementioned energy carriers. For example, Parkinson *et al.* [16] examined the economic and environmental performance of twelve low-carbon H₂ production routes, including fossil fuel reforming technologies coupled with CCS, biomass gasification without and with CCS, pyrolysis, electrolysis, and others. The cost of carbon mitigation and the proportional CO₂ reduction of those low-carbon technologies were compared to a benchmark H₂ production technology (steam methane reforming), and a tradeoff between cost and CO₂ emissions reductions was observed. The authors concluded that fossil-based pathways are less costly due to

the low costs of fossil feedstocks, but the attendant emissions reductions are modest compared to pathways that use biomass or electrolysis.

Kreutz *et al.* [17] assessed the techno-economic performance of FTL and electricity production via gasification of different mixtures of lignite and woody biomass coupled with CCS. They showed that facilities using 100% woody biomass as input produce strongly carbon-negative products and provide the best economic performance in the presence of a sufficiently high carbon emission price. Isaacs *et al.* evaluated the environmental and economic performance of four electrofuel technology pathways and found the median minimum selling price of gasification of biomass-to-liquid and power-to-liquid via electrolysis and a reverse water gas shift reaction to be 0.76 - 0.85 \$/L and 2.56 - 3.58 \$/L, respectively [18]. Gassner *et al.* [19] evaluated the economic performance of SNG production from lignocellulosic biomass via gasification and subsequent methanation. They estimated efficiencies (lower heating value basis) of 69% - 76%. The production cost of SNG was estimated to be 76–107 €/MWh for a facility having a biomass input capacity of 20 MW_{th,biomass} and 59–97 €/MWh for a 150 MW_{th,biomass} facility. So-called power-to-gas and power-to-liquid technologies that produce SNG and FTL from renewable electricity have also been evaluated for their potential in future energy systems [9, 20]. Those studies show power-to-gas and power-to-liquid to be uncompetitive with fossil routes with CO₂ capture and storage, but are more likely to be favorable if CO₂ storage is not available.

As is the case for the above-mentioned studies, most published techno-economic assessments of clean H₂, FTL, and SNG production pathways focus on evaluating different pathways for a single energy carrier, making cross-fuel comparisons difficult. Similarly, a shortcoming of the Larson *et al.* [14] and Williams *et al.* [13] macro-energy system modeling is the use of performance and cost estimates for different technology options derived from disparate literature sources.

In the work presented here, we seek to address these literature shortcomings by developing lifecycle GHG emissions and cost assessments across different low-carbon/carbon-negative H₂, FTL, and SNG production pathways. This enables more rigorous assessment of the relative value of the different fuels in a greenhouse-gas emissions constrained world. Our analysis produces estimates of life cycle GHG emissions and factory-gate levelized costs of fuel

(LCOF) as a function of carbon emissions price for each pathway, along with levelized costs of carbon mitigation (LCCM), i.e., the carbon emissions price at which the low- or negative-carbon fuel option would have the same cost as the corresponding conventional, fossil-derived benchmark fuel pathway. We also carry out parametric sensitivity analyses to assess the impact of performance and cost sensitivity on our findings.

2. Methodology

Low- and negative-carbon fuel production pathways evaluated in this work are summarized in Table 1.* For consistency across all of the pathways, the performance and capital costs of the FTL and SNG production technologies are constructed as combinations of those for a H₂ production technology and a fuel synthesis technology (as detailed in Section 2.1). This provides a realistic representation for pathways in the cases when electrolytic H₂ (produced via P4) is an input to fuels synthesis (P9 and P14 in Table 1).

For FTL and SNG pathways that start with H₂ from natural gas, the natural gas could instead be directly converted into a synthesis gas (CO + H₂) and integrated with a fuel synthesis unit. However, the resulting synthetic fuel would have a relatively high lifecycle GHG emissions intensity. Instead, our pathways use H₂ made from natural gas with CO₂ capture (P2 or P3) and processed together with carbon-neutral CO₂ (from direct air capture) to produce low-carbon FTL (P7 and P8) or SNG (P12 and P13).

For FTL or SNG pathways that start with H₂ from biomass, we produce synthesis gas by combining the bio-derived H₂ with CO made via reverse water gas shift from some of the CO₂ byproduct of the H₂ production process. In practice, the biomass might instead be gasified and then partially water-gas shifted to produce a synthesis gas with H₂/CO ratio suitable for fuel synthesis. Our approach will underestimate performance and may overestimate costs relative to that more-integrated approach but has the benefit that all pathways to FTL and SNG (regardless of starting input energy form) are being modeled on a self-consistent basis, and so allows more meaningful cross-pathway conclusions. Our sensitivity analyses help assess the robustness of these conclusions to inherent uncertainties in key modeling assumptions.

* Our analysis here is carried out in the context of the United States and therefore does not consider options using coal as a feedstock. Coal gasification coupled with CCS is unlikely to be competitive with NG reforming with CCS because of relatively low natural gas prices in the U.S.

The energy and carbon contents we assume for biomass and the different energy products are shown in Table 2. Table 3 summarizes our technical and economic input assumptions, including input feedstock intensity (IFI), CO₂ capture rate, capital cost (CAPEX), fixed operation and maintenance (FOM) cost, and variable operation and maintenance (VOM) cost. These estimates were developed from existing literature sources, as detailed in Appendices A and B. The cost and performance estimates here are assumed to be for commercially-mature technologies. Except for steam methane reforming (SMR), none of the technologies are commercially mature today, however, so what we present is a forward-looking analysis for costs that might plausibly be achieved by the mid-to-late 2030s. Consistent with this perspective, we assume that electricity generation will be largely decarbonized by then, such that delivered electricity (for electrolysis) will have lifecycle GHG emissions near zero. Even if the electricity system as a whole has not reached zero emissions, it is likely that flexible demands such as electrolyzers will run only when variable wind and solar resources are in abundance, resulting in zero marginal emissions and low electricity input prices. The next section describes each of the evaluated H₂, FTL, and SNG production pathways, and that is followed in Section 2.2 by an explanation of the methodology we use to compute key environmental and economic performance metrics.

Table 1. Hydrogen (H₂), Fischer-Tropsch liquids (FTL), and synthetic natural gas (SNG) production pathways evaluated in this study.

Fuel	Pathway	Label	Technology	Energy Input ^a
H ₂	P1	SMR	Steam methane reforming	NG
	P2	SMR-CCS	Steam methane reforming w/CCS	NG
	P3	ATR-CCS	Autothermal reforming w/CCS	NG
	P4	Electrolysis	Electrolysis	Elec
	P5	BG-H2	Gasification + water-gas-shift	Bio
	P6	BGCCS-H2	Gasification + water-gas-shift w/CCS	Bio
FTL	P7	SMR-FTL	SMR-CCS + reverse water gas shift-Fischer Tropsch synthesis (RWGS-FTS)	NG
	P8	ATR-FTL	ATR-CCS + RWGS-FTS	NG
	P9	Elec-FTL	Electrolysis + RWGS-FTS	Elec
	P10	BG-FTL	BG-H2 + RWGS-FTS	Bio
	P11	BGCCS-FTL	BGCCS-H2 + RWGS-FTS	Bio
SNG	P12	SMR-SNG	SMR-CCS + Methanation	NG
	P13	ATR-SNG	ATR-CCS + Methanation	NG
	P14	Elec-SNG	Electrolysis + Methanation	Elec
	P15	BG-SNG	BG-H2 + Methanation	Bio
	P16	BGCCS-SNG	BGCCS-H2 + Methanation	Bio

(a) NG = natural gas, Bio = biomass, Elec = Electricity

Table 2. Energy and carbon contents of biomass and fuels.^a

	Higher Heating Value, GJ _{HHV} /t	Ratio of Higher to Lower Heating Value	Carbon Intensity kg CO ₂ /GJ _{HHV}
Biomass ^b	19.8	1.07	87.9
Natural gas (or SNG)	55.5	1.11	50
H ₂	142	1.18	0
FTL	45.5	1.05	67.7

(a) Unless otherwise indicated, the energy contents of fuels are reported on a higher heating value basis in this paper.

(b) The heating values shown here are for dry biomass. Energy and carbon contents of biomass will vary by biomass type.

Table 3. Cost and performance estimates for H₂, FTL, and SNG technologies.^a Cost parameters are in 2016\$^b and given per unit of output capacity or energy. All fuel values are on a higher heating value basis.

	Technology	Input Feedstock Intensity (IFI) (GJ _{in} /GJ _{out})	Co-product ^c (GJ/GJ _{H2})	CO ₂ capture rate (%) ^d	CAPEX (\$/kW capacity)	Fixed O&M (\$/kW-year)	Var. O&M (\$/GJ)
H ₂	SMR	1.23 (NG)	0	0	511	18	0.3
	SMR-CCS	1.26 (NG)	0.024	91.2	887	26.6	0
	ATR-CCS	1.2 (NG)	0.048	94.1	776	23.3	0
	BGCCS-H2	1.78 (biomass)	- 0.023	87	2432	43.3	3.2
	BG-H2	1.78 (biomass)	- 0.079	0	2334	41.5	3.2
	Electrolysis	1.28 (electricity)	0	0	1323	14.8	0
FTL ^e	RWGS+FTS	1.47 (H ₂)	0	0	944	25.2	0.6
SNG ^f	Methanation	1.26 (H ₂)	0	0	1650	82.5	0

(a) See Appendices A and B for supporting details.

(b) To convert costs to 2016 \$ from the original dollar-year values for estimates taken from the literature, the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index, GDP deflator, or other indices were applied.

(c) Co-product is electricity in all cases. Positive values are inputs and negative values are outputs.

(d) CO₂ capture rate is the amount of carbon captured divided by carbon in the input feedstock.

(e) For RWGS-FTS pathway, 67.7 kg of carbon-neutral CO₂ (from direct air capture or bio-derived) is required to produce 1GJ_{FTL}. This process is assessed with H₂ from each of the H₂ production routes in this table, except SMR.

(f) For the methanation pathway, 50 kg carbon-neutral CO₂ (from direct air capture or bio-derived) is required to produce 1GJ_{SNG}. This process is assessed with H₂ from each of the H₂ production routes in this table, except SMR.

2.1 Synthetic fuels production pathways

2.1.1 Hydrogen

Six H₂ production technologies are evaluated, including the dominant commercial technology today, steam methane reforming (SMR). The other five technologies are SMR

coupled with CCS (SMR-CCS), autothermal reforming coupled with CCS (ATR-CCS), biomass gasification plus water gas shift (BG-H₂), biomass gasification plus water gas shift coupled with CCS (BGCCS-H₂), and electrolysis. SMR is the benchmark technology for H₂ production in our analysis: all other evaluated H₂ production technologies have lower life cycle greenhouse gases emissions than SMR but higher production costs. In the case of electricity, if the input is produced by carbon-free sources such as wind and solar, the resulting H₂ would have near-zero lifecycle GHG emissions. With BGCCS-H₂, lifecycle emissions are negative.

Natural gas reforming is the main method for H₂ production today, primarily SMR, which accounts for 95% of U.S. H₂ production [21]. SMR is a process by which the natural gas reacts with steam over a catalyst at high temperature and pressure to produce syngas (CO + H₂). Heat to drive the endothermic reactions is provided indirectly by combustion of natural gas in air. In ATR, oxygen and steam react with natural gas to form syngas in a single chamber, where heat is generated by partial combustion of the natural gas. With both SMR and ATR, the resulting CO and H₂ are subjected to water gas shifting to generate additional H₂ while converting CO to CO₂ [22]. Finally, H₂ is separated from CO₂, typically using pressure swing adsorption, resulting in near 100% purity H₂. The characteristics of SMR-CCS and ATR-CCS shown in Table 3 are based on cost and performance estimates for these technologies at a scale of 1.5 GW H₂ production capacity [23]. Appendix A provides a full description of cost and performance parameters for each fuel pathway. The ATR-CCS configuration can be operated at higher temperature and pressure than SMR-CCS, leading to higher methane conversion and higher syngas pressure, with lower input steam-to-carbon ratio, which allows smaller physical unit dimensions and higher energy outputs [23]. As a result, the ATR-CCS configuration is estimated to have a higher CO₂ capture rate, lower IFI, and lower CAPEX than SMR-CCS (Table 3).

The individual components of BGCCS-H₂ (gasification, gas cleanup, downstream syngas processing, CO₂ capture, and storage) have all been demonstrated at pilot or commercial scale. In the United States, biomass gasification processes targeting Fischer-Tropsch fuel production have been built and operated at commercial demonstration scales (> 10 million gallons per year capacity) in recent years, and additional commercialization activities are expected over the next 5 to 10 years [24]. Elsewhere, biomass gasifiers have operated successfully in power generation and SNG applications [25, 26]. No integrated BGCCS-H₂ facilities have yet been built, but some

early-mover projects are in development [27, 28], along with at least one gasification-based biomass electricity with CCS project [28]. At biomass gasification facilities, carbon dioxide capture is an intrinsic part of the process, since CO₂ removal from the syngas stream is required for optimal subsequent processing into the final product [29]. Compared to coal gasification facilities, biomass gasification facilities usually require additional feedstock preparation systems to accommodate the potential large variation in feedstock characteristics (e.g., moisture and ash content) [30]. Because the technology has not yet been commercialized, estimates of its prospective commercial techno-economic performance are uncertain. However, biomass gasification has some similarities with coal gasification, which is commercially mature, and downstream syngas processing (gas cleanup, water-gas shift, and H₂ separation via pressure swing adsorption) are similar for syngas of any origin. As such, we have based our estimates for BGCCS-H₂ in Table 3 on [31], who evaluated different coal gasification technologies for production and co-production of H₂ and electricity, and on [17], who evaluated the techno-economic performance of bio-electricity-CCS (BGCCS-el). (See Appendix A.) To maintain consistency across technologies evaluated here, we derived our performance estimates for H₂ from biomass without CCS (BG-H₂) from those for BGCCS-H₂.

Water electrolysis is a well-established method that uses electricity to split water into H₂ and O₂, but the cost of electrolytic H₂ production today is high (3 - 5 \$/kg H₂, for a capital cost of \$1,500/kW_{el}, electricity priced at \$0.03/kWh to \$0.04/kWh, efficiency of 70%, and capacity factor at 50% - 70%). With projected declines in renewable electricity costs and improvements in electrolyzer technologies, electrolytic H₂ becomes more competitive. To date, alkaline, proton exchange membrane (PEM), and solid-oxide electrolysis have been considered for H₂ production. Among these, alkaline electrolysis is the most commercialized and well-developed. PEM is slightly less mature, while solid-oxide is pre-commercial. The current capital costs for PEM are higher than for alkaline electrolyzers, but PEM is more efficient and feasibly operable flexibly in an intermittent-renewables electricity environment. Further development of PEM holds promise for lowering capital costs to below those for alkaline electrolyzers [32]. In this study, we adopt the cost and performance parameters of PEM electrolysis systems based on [33], as detailed in Appendix A.

2.1.2 Fischer-Tropsch Liquids

FTL production technologies evaluated in this study combine a H₂ production technology with a RWGS step, followed by FTS. We considered systems incorporating each of the H₂ production routes in section 2.1.1 (except for SMR). Our RWGS-FTS configuration is adapted from [29], and the cost and performance parameters of RWGS-FTS in Table 3 are based on [29] and [34], as detailed in Appendix B. H₂ and CO₂ are firstly consumed to generate CO from CO₂ via RWGS. H₂ and CO are then fed into tubular fixed-bed reactors containing a cobalt-based FT catalyst and synthesized into a mixture of hydrocarbons. The output mixture is refined into synthetic diesel, jet fuel, and liquid petroleum gas. In order to produce FTL with near-zero life-cycle GHGs emissions, the CO₂ resources used for RWGS-FTS (67.7 kg CO₂/GJ_{FTL}, Table 3 note e) must be supplied either by direct capture from air (DAC) or from a biogenic source, as discussed further in Section 2.2.

2.1.3 Synthetic natural gas

Similar to FTL pathways, our SNG production pathways are combinations of an H₂ production process and methanation. As with FTL pathways, we consider all the H₂ pathways except for SMR. The needed CO₂ input for methanation (50 kg CO₂/GJ_{SNG}, Table 3 note f) is assumed to come from DAC or biogenic sources. The methanation process involves hydrogenation of CO₂ over a catalyst (typically Ni-based). The reaction is highly exothermic, so the reactor temperature must be controlled, both to improve equilibrium yield and to avoid catalyst degradation [33, 35]. An isothermal reactor is assumed to be used in this study and the cost and performance parameters for methanation in Table 3 are based on [33], as detailed in Appendix B.

2.2 Life cycle assessment

2.2.1 Lifecycle GHG emissions analysis

We estimated life cycle GHG emissions for each pathway in Table 1. Figure 1 is a schematic representation of our carbon accounting. We considered upstream emissions associated with provision of energy and materials (Table 4), any uncaptured emissions from fossil fuels consumed at the conversion facility, photosynthetic removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere, and geologic sequestration of CO₂. Our emissions estimates also include combustion emissions at the point of fuel end-use, but not emissions that might occur between the factory gate and point of use since the latter may vary significantly depending on whether the

end-use is in transport, industry, power, or other sector. We report the life cycle CO₂-equivalent (CO₂e) emissions for each pathway, considering global warming potentials for the non-CO₂ greenhouse gases for both a 20-year timeframe (GWP₂₀) and a 100-year timeframe (GWP₁₀₀).

Figure 1. The carbon system boundaries (dashed lines) of evaluated pathways. Green boundaries represent H₂ production routes (P1-P6); orange boundaries represent FTL/SNG production routes (P7-P16). All arrows represent carbon flows (CO₂ equivalents). Arrows crossing a dashed line represent emissions to or from the atmosphere. “From atmosphere” is CO₂ that originates in the atmosphere and is removed via direct air capture or is produced from photosynthesized CO₂, i.e., biomass.

Biomass used for energy is generally considered carbon-neutral if is grown on an annual or shorter cycle and after harvesting the carbon it contains cycles back to the atmosphere as CO₂. If some or all of the biogenic CO₂ is instead captured and sequestered underground, the process involves net removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere, i.e., the biomass conversion to energy results in negative emissions. The biomass used for fuel production here is assumed to be residues of annual agricultural activities or perennial grasses grown on land not currently in use for agriculture. As such, emissions associated with direct or indirect land use change are negligible. Direct upstream emissions associated with production, harvesting, transport, and processing of biomass feedstocks are included in our emissions accounting, based on parameters for switchgrass quantified in the GREET model [36].

For the natural gas supply chain, many studies have estimated the upstream GHG emissions, and a wide variation in estimates is evident in the literature. Balcombe *et al.* [37]

reviewed 424 papers and found that reported GHGs emissions from the entire supply chain (from extraction to distribution) ranged from 0.2% to 10% of produced methane, with mean and median values of 2.2% and 1.6%, respectively. Per unit of natural gas produced, the range is 2.7 to 32.8 g CO₂e/MJ_{HHV}, with a median of 13.4 gCO₂e/MJ_{HHV}, assuming GWP₁₀₀ = 34 for methane. Littlefield *et al* [38] used recent series of methane emissions measurement campaigns from 8 studies. They estimated that 1.7 % of methane is emitted from the natural gas supply chain, with 95% confidence intervals from 1.3% to 2.2%. They translated the 1.7% emissions rate to 13.8 g CO₂e/MJ considering GWP₁₀₀ = 36 and 28.6 g CO₂e/MJ considering GWP₂₀ = 87. Both of the aforementioned studies reviewed a large number of published studies and found nearly identical estimates of the median emissions considering GWP₁₀₀ (i.e., 13.4 gCO₂e/MJ_{HHV} and 13.8 g CO₂e/MJ_{HHV}). Littlefield *et al* [38] reported median values for both GWP₁₀₀ and GWP₂₀, so we have adopted those values for our analysis (Table 4).

The electricity used for electrolysis is assumed to be generated from wind or solar energy, with zero GHG emissions. The sources of CO₂ consumed in FTL and SNG pathways (P7-P16 in Table 1), i.e., biomass or direct air capture, are carbon neutral and thus do not contribute to life cycle emissions. For all pathways involving CO₂ capture and storage, we assumed storage in geological formations from which there is no leakage over 20- and 100-year timeframes.

Emissions associated with downstream transportation of the fuel products are not included for any of the pathways, since these will vary significantly with local geographic details and end-uses. Emissions during manufacturing and installation of conversion facilities are also not included.

Table 4. Upstream carbon intensity (*UCI*) for energy and materials

	Unit ^a	100-year (GWP-100)	20-year (GWP-20)	REF
Biomass production & harvesting & transportation (<i>UCI_{Bio}</i>)	kg CO ₂ e/GJ _{Bio}	5.08	5.09	[36]
Natural gas - production, processing, transmission, distribution (<i>UCI_{NG}</i>)	kg CO ₂ e/GJ _{NG}	13.8	28.6	[38]

(a) These are per GJ_{HHV}.

The functional unit for our analysis is 1 GJ_{HHV} of fuel output (i.e., of H₂, FTL, or SNG), and the GHGs associated with energy and material consumption are expressed on a functional unit basis, tCO₂e/GJ_{HHV}. The life cycle GHG emissions of H₂ production technologies is determined from

$$GHG_{(P)} = (UCI_{Bio} - CC_{Bio} \times CCR_p) \times IFI_{P,Bio} + (UCI_{NG} + CC_{NG} \times (1 - CCR_p)) \times IFI_{P,NG} \quad (1)$$

where the subscript P refers to an individual pathway (P1-P6, Table 1); main input feedstock type is subscripted Bio for biomass and NG for natural gas; CC refers to the carbon content (Table 2); IFI is the input feedstock intensity (Table 3); CCR is the CO₂ capture rate (Table 3); and UCI is the carbon intensity of upstream activities (Table 4).

For FTL and SNG pathways that integrate BGCCS-H₂ with RWGS-FTS (P11) or with RWGS-methanation (P16), the assumption is made that some of the CO₂ captured in the BGCCS-H₂ process would be used as input to the RWGS-FTS or methanation process. The life cycle GHGs of the integrated process are then determined as the product of the life cycle GHGs of the BGCCS-H₂ pathway (in kg CO_{2e}/GJ_{H₂}) and the IFI of fuel synthesis technology (1.47 GJ_{H₂}/GJ_{FTL} for RWGS-FTS and 1.26 GJ_{H₂}/GJ_{SNG} for methanation, as in Table 3), plus the carbon intensity of FTL or SNG (Table 2). For other FTL and SNG production pathways (P7-P10, P12 and P13), the external CO₂ resources used in these pathways are assumed to be carbon-neutral (e.g., from DAC or bio-derived), and the life cycle GHGs for these pathways are calculated by multiplying the lifecycle GHG emissions of the H₂ production pathway by the IFI for RWGS-FTS or methanation.

2.2.2 Lifecycle cost analysis

Our cost analyses account for CAPEX, FOM cost, non-fuel VOM cost (Table 3), energy and materials cost (i.e., biomass, electricity, natural gas, and CO₂ resources), and CO₂ transportation and storage cost (Table 5) over the book life of a facility. For the carbon-neutral CO₂ resources needed for several of the FTL and SNG pathways, we assume a cost of \$180/tCO₂. This is approximately the average of our cost estimates for CO₂ captured and delivered from DAC, BGCCS-H₂, and BGCCS-electricity technologies, as detailed in Appendix C and Supplementary Information. Finally, levelized costs of fuel (LCOF, \$/GJ) are calculated assuming a 15-year book life, 10% weighted average cost of capital and 85% capacity factor, except for electrolysis, which is assumed to have a capacity factor of 55%. The lower capacity factor for electrolysis is consistent with values found in the Net-Zero America study [14] for electrolysis operating in the context of the U.S. economy when it reaches net-zero emissions. LCOF values are calculated both without and with assumed carbon emission costs charged for

the net life cycle emissions associated with a pathway. If the net life cycle emissions are negative, the carbon emissions cost is a credit against other components of the LCOF.

We also compute levelized costs of carbon mitigation (LCCM) for each pathway[16]. The LCCM was adopted from Parkinson *et al* [16], and it is defined as the incremental economic cost incurred for a process divided by the environmental gain associated with the process relative to the corresponding benchmark process:

$$LCCM_P = \frac{(LCOF_P - LCOF_{benchmark})[\$ \text{ per GJ energy}]}{(GHG_{benchmark} - GHG_P)[t \text{ CO}_2e \text{ per GJ energy}]} \quad (2)$$

The numerator here is the difference between LCOF (\$/GJ) for an evaluated pathway and the carbon-intensive benchmark pathway for that fuel product. The denominator is the difference in life cycle GHGs (tCO_{2e}/GJ) between the evaluated pathway and the benchmark pathway. The benchmark technologies for H₂, FTL and SNG are SMR (P1), petroleum jet fuel, and natural gas, respectively. (The LCOF for the latter two are the prices given in Table 5.) The cost and GHG emissions of SMR (P1) will be determined in the following section. The upstream GHGs associated with conventional jet fuel production (i.e., crude oil extraction through refining) is adapted from the GREET model [36], which gives 0.012 tCO_{2e}/GJ (GWP₁₀₀) and 0.017 tCO_{2e}/GJ (GWP₂₀). The life cycle GHGs of jet fuel is the sum of upstream emissions and the carbon content of the fuel (i.e., 0.067 tCO_{2e}/GJ), or 0.079 tCO_{2e}/GJ (GWP₁₀₀) and 0.084 tCO_{2e}/GJ (GWP₂₀). For the natural gas benchmark, life cycle GHGs is the sum of the upstream GHGs in Table 4 and the carbon content (i.e., 0.050 tCO_{2e}/GJ_{NG}), or 0.0638 tCO_{2e}/GJ (GWP₁₀₀) and 0.0786 tCO_{2e}/GJ (GWP₂₀). LCCM reflects the additional costs incurred per tonne of CO₂-equivalent emissions reduced using a low/negative emissions pathway instead of the corresponding benchmark pathway. LCCM can be thought of as the carbon emission price at which the evaluated technology and benchmark technology reach cost parity.

Table 5. Parameter assumptions (2016\$)

	Unit	Value
CO ₂ resource (DAC or BioCCS)	\$/t CO ₂	180
Jet fuel refinery-gate price ^a	\$/GJ	8.9
Natural gas wholesale price ^b	\$/GJ	3.2
Biomass delivered price ^c	\$/GJ	5.1
Electricity price (except electrolysis) ^d	\$/GJ	12.5
Electricity price (electrolysis) ^d	\$/GJ	9.7
CO ₂ transportation & storage cost ^e	\$/t CO ₂	35
Capacity factor (except electrolysis) ^f	%	85

Capacity factor – electrolysis ^f	%	55
(a) Price assumed for the Upper Midwestern U.S. in 2030 by Larson, <i>et al.</i> [14], which derives from the EIA [39] Low Oil Price Case crude oil price in 2030 of \$45/bbl (2018\$).		
(b) Price assumed for the Upper Midwestern U.S. in 2030 by Larson, <i>et al.</i> [14], which derives from the EIA [39] High Oil and Gas Resource Technology Case natural gas price in 2030.		
(c) The majority of biomass supplied for energy in the modeling by Larson <i>et al.</i> [14] (page 181) has delivered costs of \$100/t _{dry} (5.1 \$/GJ) or less.		
(d) Wholesale electricity prices for a U.S. grid with large solar and wind generation will vary with time of day and season of the year. In modeling of a future solar/wind heavy generating fleet in the U.S. ([40], page 77, Supplementary Information), \$45/MWh (12.5 \$/GJ) is the average marginal cost of generation for the whole year, and \$35/MWh (9.7 \$/GJ) is the average marginal cost of generation for about half of the year.		
(e) In modeling by Larson, <i>et al.</i> [14] (page 210), the majority of CO ₂ captured and stored in the U.S. by 2050 has transport and storage costs of \$35/tCO ₂ or less.		
(f) Capacity factors are based on those assumed or calculated in modeling by Larson, <i>et al.</i> [14]. For example, see page 80 of Larson, <i>et al.</i> for calculated electrolysis capacity factors.		

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Levelized cost of fuel and life cycle CO₂ emissions

Figure 2 shows LCOF values (with no carbon price included) and life cycle GHG emissions for each of the sixteen pathways.

H₂ production routes have lower LCOF ranges than FTL and SNG for the same feedstock input, ranging from 7 – 12 \$/GJ for natural gas reforming technologies, to 23 \$/GJ for electrolysis, 24 \$/GJ for BG-H₂, and 30 \$/GJ for BGCCS-H₂. That natural gas H₂ production technologies (P1-P3) have significantly lower production costs than pathways using biomass is not surprising: natural gas reforming is much less capital intensive, has lower input feedstock intensity (Table 3), and lower input feedstock costs (Table 5). The electrolysis pathway has an intermediate level of capital cost between the natural gas and biomass routes, but operates with a lower capacity factor (Table 5) and more expensive input energy (Table 5), making it also more costly than natural gas routes.

While production costs are lowest with natural gas technologies, their life cycle GHG emissions are the highest. The H₂ benchmark technology (SMR) has estimated emissions of 0.078 t CO_{2e}/GJ H₂ (GWP₁₀₀) and 0.097 CO_{2e}/GJ H₂ (GWP₂₀). The life cycle GHG emissions are reduced by 60-70% for natural gas pathways coupled with CCS (SMR-CCS and ATR-CCS). The reductions are not deeper despite having CO₂ capture rates above 90% at the conversion phase (Table 3), because emissions remain from upstream natural gas production, processing, and transportation. We also observe a significant difference in life cycle GHG emissions for the

natural gas pathways when GWP₂₀ is used instead of GWP₁₀₀, as expected based on the contribution that natural gas leakage plays in the upstream emissions. Differences between GWP₂₀ and GWP₁₀₀ lifecycle GHG emissions for pathways that use biomass or electricity are much less significant. The BG-H₂ and electrolysis routes have zero or near-zero life cycle emissions because emissions at the conversion site (net of photosynthesis in the BG-H₂ case) are comparable to or lower than for natural gas conversion, and upstream GHG emissions are much smaller. Finally, BGCCS-H₂ has negative GHG emissions due to capture and sequestration of biogenic CO₂ at the conversion facility.

There are clear tradeoffs between cost and environmental performance. For H₂ production routes, natural gas reforming technologies exhibit lower LCOF but higher GHGs. BGCCS-H₂ has the highest LCOF but the lowest GHGs by a large margin. Electrolysis and BG-H₂ lie somewhere in between. These observations are consistent with other studies of H₂ production routes, e.g. [16].

Figure 2. LCOF without carbon price (top panel) and life cycle GHG emissions with GWP₁₀₀ and GWP₂₀ (bottom panel) for H₂, FTL, and SNG production pathways.

FTL production exhibits much higher LCOFs than H₂ production, ranging from 35 \$/GJ for natural gas routes with CCS, 42- 48 \$/GJ for biomass routes, and 53 \$/GJ for the electrolysis-based route. The relative ranking among the FTL pathways for different input feedstocks are similar to those of the H₂ production pathways except for the electrolytic pathway, which is the most expensive of the FTL pathways, but not the H₂ pathways. All FTL pathways exhibit higher costs (3 to 6 times higher), but lower GHG emissions than the corresponding benchmark values. FTL from natural gas has the lowest LCOFs, but highest GHG emissions. The BG-FTL pathway has relatively high LCOF, but much lower GHG emissions. Similar to the BGCCS-H₂ pathway, BGCCS-FTL also has strongly negative emissions. Elec-FTL has the highest LCOF and zero GHG emissions.

Finally, the LCOFs of SNG (35 to 50 \$/GJ) are similar to FTL LCOFs for pathways using the same input feedstock (P7-P11). LCOFs for SNG are 10 to 15 times higher than our assumed benchmark natural gas price of 3.2 \$/GJ (Table 5). In terms of environmental performance, all of the evaluated SNG technologies have lower life cycle GHGs than natural gas. Natural gas reforming routes have emissions of about half of the benchmark emissions for GWP₁₀₀ and about two-thirds for GWP₂₀. Electrolysis and BG routes have zero/near-zero emissions, and the BGCCS route has negative emissions.

3.2 Levelized Cost of Carbon Mitigation (LCCM)

Although LCOF and life cycle GHGs are widely used to assess the economic and environmental performance of emerging technologies, an additional metric, the levelized cost of carbon mitigation (LCCM), provides additional insight into the relative value of these technologies in the context of decarbonization. As previously noted, LCCM is the additional cost for a low/negative emissions fuel production pathway per tonne of CO_{2e} emissions reduced compared to its corresponding carbon-intensive benchmark technology. LCCM can be thought of as a break-even CO_{2e} emissions price, i.e., the emissions price or subsidy for emissions reduction at which the cost for the lower-emission technology equals that for the benchmark technology. Again, we consider the LCCM under a shorter-term (GWP₂₀) and a longer-term

(GWP₁₀₀) perspective. Results for 15 low carbon and negative carbon emissions technologies are shown in Figure 3. Since SMR (P1) is the benchmark technology for H₂ production, it is excluded from the LCCM analysis.

All the natural gas pathways exhibit higher life cycle GHGs over a 20-year time horizon than a 100-year horizon (Figure 2). However, ATR-CCS and SMR-CCS have nearly identical LCCM values for the two time horizons. This is because the difference in emissions between SMR and ATR/SMR-CCS are identical under GWP₁₀₀ and GWP₂₀, and the difference in LCOFs is small. In contrast to the natural gas pathways, LCCM values for biomass or electricity pathways are lower for the 20-year horizon than for the 100-year horizon. This results because the upstream life cycle emissions for biomass and electricity are relatively insensitive to the time-horizon (Table 4), while the emissions for the benchmark pathway are higher for the 20-year horizon than for the 100-year horizon.

Figure 3. LCCM of H₂, FTL, and SNG pathways with biomass (blue), clean electricity (yellow), and natural gas (blue) as feedstocks; GWP₁₀₀ (dashed) and GWP₂₀ (dotted) are used to reflect long-term and short-term climate impacts.

In Figure 3 the H₂ production pathways generally have the lowest LCCMs, but these span a significant range – from around 60 \$/t CO₂e for ATR-CCS to 190 (GWP₂₀) and 240 \$/t CO₂e (GWP₁₀₀) for BG-H₂. The LCCM for ATR-CCS is lower than for the other natural gas option, SMR-CCS, due to both the lower LCOF and greater GHG emissions reductions for ATR-CCS (Figure 2). The SMR-CCS and ATR-CCS pathways are societally cost competitive today for H₂ production, considering that the average social costs of carbon in the U.S. for 2020 and 2025 have recently been estimated to be 76 and 83 \$/tCO₂e (for 2.5% discount rate) [41], respectively. BGCCS-H₂ has LCCM values less than double those for ATR-CCS despite triple the LCOF (Figure 2), because of the highly-negative life cycle GHG emissions for BGCCS-H₂. The LCCMs for BG-H₂ and electrolysis are comparable to each other and higher than for BGCCS-H₂ due primarily to much lower avoided life cycle GHG emissions.

The lack of correlation between LCOF and LCCM (compare Figures 2 and 3) illustrates the importance of the LCCM metric, alongside simpler metrics like LCOF, when considering cost-effective options for decarbonization of fuel pathways: both incremental costs and avoided emissions relative to carbon-intensive benchmarks vary with the low/negative emission pathway, making simpler comparisons potentially misleading.

FTL production pathways are more costly to decarbonize than H₂ pathways for the same input feedstock, with LCCMs ranging from 200 to 590 \$/t CO₂e (GWP₁₀₀) or 190 to 1100 \$/t CO₂e (GWP₂₀). The BGCCS-FTL pathway sits at the low end of this range, which suggests it will initially be the most attractive FTL option when/where carbon-emission pricing (or equivalent policies) are in effect. In contrast, the BG-FTL pathway has a much higher LCCM, despite a lower LCOF, because of the much less significant reductions in GHG emissions it achieves compared with the BGCCS-FTL option (Figure 2). The LCCM for natural gas FTL pathways assuming GWP₁₀₀ are modestly higher than for BG-FTL, but are much higher for GWP₂₀ due to the much higher sensitivity of natural gas pathways than biomass pathways to the contribution of upstream emissions to life cycle emissions. The electrolysis pathway has the second highest LCCM over a 100-year time horizon. Over a 20-year horizon, the electrolysis LCCM exceeds those for biomass, but is far lower than for the natural gas pathways due to the sensitivity of the latter to upstream emissions.

Finally, LCCMs for SNG production range from 250 \$/t CO₂e to 910 \$/t CO₂e (GWP₁₀₀) or 240 \$/t CO₂e to 1200 \$/t CO₂e (GWP₂₀). BGCCS-SNG is at the low end of this range. All the other pathways have much higher LCCM. One may observe in Figure 2 that BG-SNG, electrolysis-SNG, SMR-SNG and ATR-SNG (P12 – P15) all have LCOF and life cycle GHG emissions comparable to those for their FTL counterparts (P7 - P10). But, the LCCM for the SNG pathways are considerably higher than for the corresponding FTL pathways primarily because of the characteristics of the SNG and FTL benchmarks used in the LCCM calculation: the SNG benchmark, natural gas, has a much lower cost and emissions intensity than the benchmark for FTL, refined fossil jet fuel.

Based on the LCCM values, one may conclude that as the willingness to pay for carbon-emission reductions increases, first H₂, then liquid fuels, then pipeline gas become economical to decarbonize. Of these three options, H₂ and SNG are both gaseous fuels and thus potentially in competition with each other to displace fossil natural gas. To evaluate potential competition between these fuel pathways, it is appropriate to recompute LCCM for BGCCS-H₂ using natural gas as the benchmark. This gives a value of \$140/tCO₂e (GWP₁₀₀), which is still far lower than the LCCM for BGCCS-SNG (\$250/tCO₂e, GWP₁₀₀). Furthermore, BGCCS-H₂ has higher negative life cycle CO₂ emissions than BGCCS-SNG (on an equivalent energy basis), which further suggests the favorability of BGCCS-H₂ over BGCCS-SNG in the context of decarbonization. Thus, the displacement of natural gas by H₂ (BGCCS-H₂ in particular), where possible, will generally be more favorable economically and emissions-wise than displacement by SNG. One such application could take advantage of the existing natural gas pipeline infrastructure by blending BGCCS-H₂ into the pipeline. This appears to be technically feasible without modification of the pipeline up to a limit of 7% H₂ on HHV energy basis (equivalent to 20% on volume basis) [42]. Blending 7% BGCCS-H₂ would reduce the life cycle CO₂ emissions of the pipeline gas mixture by 20%. (BGCCS-SNG blended with natural gas at 7% would reduce life cycle CO₂ emissions of pipeline gas by 18%, but of course it could be blended at much higher blend fractions and achieve higher emissions reductions as a result.) In other applications, H₂ might be blended with natural gas or completely replace it, for example in gas turbines for electricity generation. Since downstream costs and emissions for transportation are not accounted for in our study, it is uncertain whether costs for H₂ transport, storage, and use would significantly affect our results. Unlike H₂, SNG can use existing pipeline infrastructure directly

and provide energy to existing end uses without modifications. Future work should evaluate the full supply chain, including fuel delivery and use.

3.3 LCCM sensitivity analysis

To help gain insight into the most important parameters, we carried out parametric sensitivity analyses focusing on LCCM, with one parameter value changed at a time while keeping others at the baseline values used to generate Figure 3. For the sensitivity analysis, we consider only the 100-year time horizon and test sensitivities to capacity factor, capital cost, CO₂ resources price, jet fuel price, electricity price, biomass price, and natural gas price. In addition, we also considered the impacts of IFI on LCCM. We consider parameter value variations of $\pm 10\%$ of the baseline values. Figure 4 shows results for H₂ (left panel), FTL (middle panel), and SNG (right panel), Figure 5 shows the sensitivity to IFI of all the pathways, and a summary table in Supplementary Information document (see “Sensitivity ranking” tab) shows the ranking of all the sensitivity parameters.

Figure 4. Variation in LCCM for 100-year time horizon relative to values in Figure 3: H₂ pathways (left panel); FTL pathways (middle panel); SNG pathways (right panel). Each parameter variation is +10% (green) and -10% (red). The resulting changes are proportional to the magnitudes of input changes because results are linear with changes in each of the examined parameters. For sensitivity parameters without any results indicated, mean the impacts were zero or negligible. The x-axis units are percent of the LCCM value in Figure 3 for the corresponding pathway.

For H₂ pathways, the LCCM results are most sensitive to capital cost (CAPEX) and capacity factor. The LCCMs of ATR-CSS and SMR-CCS are negligibly impacted by changes in natural gas price (and so those LCCM results are not shown). The insensitivity is because these technologies and their benchmark technology (SMR) both use NG and have very similar IFI values. For BG-H₂ and BGCCS-H₂, sensitivities of LCCM to natural gas and biomass prices are moderate: higher natural gas price contributes to lowering the LCCM, and higher biomass prices lead to higher LCCM. Biomass price uncertainty is connected to biomass availability, which directly affects the capacity factor of a plant. For example, if biomass supply were impacted by weather, the capacity factor might be reduced. To maintain a relatively high capacity factor, additional costs for biomass feedstocks might be incurred, for example to compete with other users in the face of limited supply or to add storage of biomass to buffer supply variability.

For electrolysis, besides CAPEX and capacity factor, the electricity price is also an important driver. However, it should be noted that electricity price and capacity factor are related in ways that moderate changes in LCCM with changes in either of those parameters. In general, electricity price increases with increasing electricity demand. Maintaining a high electrolysis capacity factor would correspond to greater consumption during periods of higher overall electricity demand, so average input electricity prices would be higher as well. In contrast, average input electricity prices are likely if lower capacity factors are accepted for the electrolysis system. It should be noted that electrolysis technology may see dramatic reductions in CAPEX in the longer term. If electrolysis cost reductions follow those observed for similar modular technologies, such as lithium ion battery packs, the cost learning rate, i.e., the percentage reduction in capital cost for each doubling of cumulative production, might be of the order of 18% [43]. Applying this rate to PEM electrolyzers, the installed capacity of which in the U.S. today is 0.172 GW [44] with current capital costs around \$2000/kW_{el} (equivalent to \$2560/kW_{H2} for an efficiency of 78%) [45], would result in costs reducing to 400 \$/kW_{H2} (312 \$/kW_{el}, or less than 70% of the cost we have assumed in our baseline analysis) when cumulative capacity reaches 100 GW. At \$400/kW_{H2}, the LCCM for electrolytic H₂ would be 120 \$/t CO_{2e}, putting it on par with our estimate of BGCCS-H₂ in Figure 3.

In the case of LCCM for FTL and SNG, again CAPEX and capacity factor are crucial drivers. Also, higher prices for benchmark energy carriers (i.e., jet fuel and natural gas) have an impact, decreasing LCCM, though not as significantly as changes in capex and capacity factor. In contrast, higher feedstock costs (i.e., natural gas, electricity, biomass, and CO₂) result in more marked increases in LCCM. For FTL and SNG pathways involving natural gas with CCS, the cost of CO₂ inputs significantly impacts LCCM. For those pathways, the CO₂ resources account for almost 30% of the LCOF under the baseline assumption of \$180/t for carbon-neutral CO₂. The \$180/t CO₂ used in this manuscript was the average of estimated CO₂ costs from DAC and BECCS facilities. Cost estimates for DAC vary widely in the literature. For example, the cost from Climeworks was \$600/t CO₂ in 2017 [46, 47]. A review summary by McQueen *et al* suggests net CO₂ removal costs from DAC range from 126-780 \$/t CO₂ [48]. If the cost of DAC is higher than we have assumed, this will result in even worse performance than the results we have shown for SNG/FTL production pathways involving natural gas with CCS. A less costly source of carbon input could be from the natural gas feedstock itself, but there would be little or no residual carbon that could be captured for storage, which would make the life cycle GHGs even higher than for petroleum-derived jet fuel and significantly increase LCCM compared with use of carbon-neutral CO₂. This suggests that it would be beneficial from a LCCM perspective to integrate ATR-CCS-H₂ (or SMR-CCS-H₂), BGCCS-H₂, and RWGS-FTS for production of low- or negative-carbon FTL. Similar to the electrolysis-H₂ pathway, future cost learning for electrolysis systems would affect the performance of Elec-FTL and Elec-SNG pathways. However, by using the aforementioned learned-down CAPEX (i.e., 400 \$/kW_{H₂} for PEM electrolysis), and keeping other parameters unchanged, the breakeven carbon price (or LCCM) of Elec-FTL and Elec-SNG pathways, 420 \$/t CO_{2e} and 590 \$/t CO_{2e}, respectively, are still much higher than BGCCS-FTL and BGCCS-SNG.

In addition to aforementioned parameters, we also varied the IFI of each pathway by $\pm 10\%$ to assess the sensitivity of LCCM to this parameter (Figure 5). The LCCM of technologies that use natural gas as feedstock are very sensitive to IFI, because as IFI increases, an increasing amount of natural gas is required for H₂ production, leading to higher feedstock costs and higher greenhouse gases emissions. This also corresponds to an increase in the cost penalty (increased numerator of LCCM), and a decrease in the difference of environmental benefits (decreased denominator). As a result, the LCCM of those technologies are significantly affected by the IFI.

The LCCM for the electrolysis and bioenergy pathways (without CCS) similarly experience changes in LCOF and life cycle GHGs emissions when IFI is changed. Biomass and renewable electricity have much lower life cycle GHGs emissions as compared to NG, so those pathways are less sensitive to IFI than NG-fueled pathways, meaning that overall improvements in conversion efficiency are more critical for natural gas-fueled pathways. Finally, biomass coupled with CCS pathways are the least sensitive to changes in IFI. For the BGCCS-H2 pathway, changing IFI by 10% results in less than a 1% change in LCCM. Furthermore, the LCCM of BGCCS-FTL and BGCCS-SNG actually decreases with increasing IFI: higher IFI increases LCOF due to greater consumption of feedstock, but also increases the amount of CO₂ captured. As a result, the cost penalty with increased IFI (i.e., the increase in the LCCM numerator) is more than offset by the environmental gain (increase in the denominator), and LCCM falls with increasing IFI.

Figure 5. Changes of LCCM (GWP₁₀₀) when changing the IFI by ±10%. Positive (negative) values are increases (decreases) compared to the baseline LCCM (i.e., values shown in Figure 3). The resulting changes are proportional to the magnitudes of input changes because results are linear with changes in each of the examined parameters. For the FTL and SNG pathways, only the IFI associated with the H₂ production portion of the process is modified.

In summary, the IFI sensitivity analysis indicates the importance of increasing feedstock utilization efficiencies of technologies that exhibit positive life cycle GHGs emissions. In contrast, for BGCCS- pathways, which have negative GHG emissions, our results suggest the favorability of deploying BGCCS- technologies that are both less efficient and less capital intensive. Similar conclusions have been found by Mac Dowell and Fajardy [49]. Because sustainably-produced biomass-energy feedstocks are limited resources, the added environmental benefits of less energy-efficient BGCCS- facilities must be carefully weighed against the need to meet overall demands for carbon-neutral fuels made via biomass conversion.

3.4 LCOF as a function of the carbon price

The LCCM (Eqn 2) is effectively the carbon emissions price at which the cost of the lower-emitting fuel option is the same as that for the corresponding higher-emitting benchmark option. To better understand how different fuel options compare at different carbon emission prices, LCOF values can be recalculated to include a carbon price and plotted as a function of that carbon price (Figure 6). The y-intercepts in Figure 6 correspond to the LCOF values in Figure 2, and the x-value where each option intersects the benchmark LCOF (dashed line) corresponds to the LCCM values in Figure 3. The slope of LCOF of each technology is determined by the life cycle GHGs emissions (Figure 2, lower panel), with negative life cycle GHGs corresponding to negative slopes. For pathways that require an input of external carbon-neutral CO₂ (e.g., P7-P10 and P12-P13), the cost of the CO₂ used to calculate the LCOF values in Figure 6 is fixed at \$180/t, regardless of the carbon emissions price. This assumes that a fuel producer would secure long-term access to carbon-neutral CO₂ at a fixed price either by building a CO₂ capture facility on site or entering into a long-term contract with an external entity providing the CO₂. On-site capture might be via DAC for facilities using natural gas or electricity as primary input. For a biomass facility, a CO₂ capture unit could be integrated into the facility to provide just the CO₂ separation needed for fuels synthesis (as distinct from the full CO₂ separation that occurs with a BGCCS-H₂ facility).

At zero carbon price, the benchmark fossil fuels have the lowest LCOF (dashed lines in Figure 6). As carbon price increases, the benchmark LCOFs increase rapidly, while the clean pathways, which have near-zero or negative carbon emissions, become relatively more favorable. For H₂ production pathways (Figure 6a), the conventional SMR pathway exhibits the lowest

LCOF for carbon prices less than \$63/t CO₂e. When the carbon price is between \$63/t CO₂e and \$130/t CO₂e, the ATR-CCS pathway is the most favorable. Above \$130/t CO₂e, BGCCS-H₂ is the least-cost pathway. Other H₂ pathways have higher LCOFs, but all intersect the benchmark LCOF at carbon prices no greater than 250 \$/t CO₂e.

For the FTL and SNG pathways (Figure 6a and 6b), the benchmark fossil fuel options have the lowest LCOF until the carbon price reaches \$200/t CO₂e and \$260/t CO₂e, respectively. At prices higher than these, BGCCS-FTL and BGCCS-SNG exhibit the lowest LCOF because of the significant negative emissions associated with these pathways. Other production pathways intersect the benchmark pathway at carbon prices between \$450/t and \$600/t for FTL production and over 700 \$/t for SNG production (off-scale in Figure 6).

Figure 6. LCOF for H₂, FTL, and SNG production pathways as a function of carbon price. The lifecycle GHG emissions of each pathway is based on GWP₁₀₀. Dashed lines represent the benchmark pathways for H₂, FTL, and SNG.

4. Conclusions

Many prior studies have assessed the economic and environmental performance of pathways for clean fuel production. Most such studies evaluate only technologies for a single fuel product, e.g., hydrogen (H₂), Fischer-Tropsch liquids (FTL), or synthetic natural gas (SNG). Our study provides self-consistent lifecycle greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and cost assessments across production pathways for all three of these fuels, each using natural gas,

biomass, or electricity as the primary input feedstock. Results have been reported in terms of levelized costs of fuel (LCOF) both for zero and non-zero carbon emission prices, life cycle GHG emissions, and levelized costs of carbon mitigation (LCCM) relative to a corresponding benchmark (high carbon-emitting) option. LCCM is especially important for understanding the relative cost-effectiveness of options for decarbonizing liquid and gaseous fuels. It often provides a significantly different relative ranking of pathways than the LCOF or life cycle GHG metric.

Our results support the idea that H₂ has a critical role to play in transitions to decarbonized fuel systems. We find that LCOFs for decarbonized H₂ are significantly lower than for low-carbon liquid fuel or synthetic natural gas for the same feedstock inputs. This pattern is also reflected in LCCM values, with H₂ made from natural gas with CO₂ capture and storage offering the lowest LCCM (about 60 \$/tCO_{2e}, in a U.S. context). This suggests that decarbonized H₂ from natural gas could enter the fuels sector earlier than decarbonized liquids or synthetic natural gas. As carbon mitigation ambitions grow, and the effective price of GHG emissions grows, H₂ made from biomass with CO₂ capture and storage (BGCCS-H₂) becomes the more attractive H₂ option on a LCOF basis, and the highly-negative emissions for this pathway results in a declining LCOF as the carbon emissions price increases. Meanwhile, the LCOF for other decarbonized H₂ pathways increase with GHG emissions price, albeit more slowly than the LCOF for the benchmark pathway, and so these options eventually compete favorably with the benchmark when emission prices are high enough.

In the case of decarbonized FTL and SNG, BGCCS pathways are the most competitive on a LCOF basis above certain threshold carbon price levels. The breakeven carbon price is 190 \$/t for BGCCS-FTL and 250 \$/t CO₂ for BGCCS-SNG. The LCOF for pathways to decarbonized FTL and SNG using natural gas, electricity, and biomass without CCS have much higher breakeven carbon prices (> 400 \$/t). This suggests that those pathways, at least in the U.S. context, are likely to be deployed only where the more-competitive biomass coupled with CCS option is not available. Furthermore, if sufficient negative emissions are available at a marginal cost below these very high breakeven prices, it may never make economic sense to pursue these decarbonization pathways. Additionally, in the case of SNG, another competitor is decarbonized H₂, which has the potential to be used in many applications where natural gas is used today.

Our analysis has assumed commercially-mature performance and cost levels, but most of the technology pathways we have considered are still far from commercially mature and so our estimates must be considered uncertain. Our sensitivity analysis shows that the economic competitiveness of many pathways is largely influenced by capital costs and capacity factors. Feedstock costs are also influential for certain types of technology (e.g., electricity price for electrolysis, carbon neutral CO₂ for fuel synthesis), but not sensitive if the benchmark technology and evaluated technology used the same type of feedstocks (e.g., SMR/ATR-CCS for H₂ production). When natural gas is used as feedstock, input feedstock intensity (IFI) is an especially important parameter as it affects both feedstock costs and GHG emissions. One particularly interesting finding is that for biomass pathways with CCS, it may be more favorable economically to sacrifice some energy conversion efficiency to reduce capital-intensity, since lower fuel conversion efficiency is compensated by greater negative CO₂ emissions, which may outweigh the reduction in fuel production depending on the relative value of fuel and negative emissions. Future work should aim to improve and refine cost and performance estimates, while maintaining self-consistency in the estimates across the different fuel pathways. We can also suggest several additional directions for future work to help address some limitations of the present work.

First, our estimates of life cycle GHG emissions do not include emissions associated with manufacturing and construction of the infrastructure associated with each pathway. For conventional fossil fuel pathways, the latter emissions contribute almost negligibly to total lifecycle GHG emissions. For example, the contribution from commissioning and decommissioning a coal fired power plant has been estimated to be 0.8 - 1.3 kg CO₂e/MWh [50, 51], compared with emissions from operation of the plant of 800 – 1000 kg CO₂e/MWh. For low-carbon pathways, however, the infrastructure emissions may be a significant fraction of total lifecycle GHG emissions. While such emissions may still be small in absolute value, understanding their contribution to lifecycle GHG emissions will be important, especially as net-zero emissions targets are approached.

Second, our assessments are not specific to the fuel delivery or end-use system. Delivery and end-use specific assessments may provide additional important insights. FTL and SNG are drop-in fuels that can be used directly in existing engines and infrastructure, and so may involve relatively modest incremental end-use downstream costs and emissions. However, for H₂, if

usage in a future low-carbon world expands beyond the primarily captive uses it has today, the added costs for delivery and distribution could be significant. For example, it's estimated that today the cost for H₂ delivery and dispensing (excluding H₂ production) at a rate of 450 kg/day by liquid tanker trucks is \$11/kg, or \$77/GJ (ten times our LCOF production cost estimate for SMR) [52]. Given the high costs and the uncertainty associated with H₂ delivery and dispensing, it is unclear how they would affect the results from a lifecycle perspective. Such costs and any associated downstream emissions might change our cost and/or emissions orderings of H₂ versus FTL and SNG, though LCCM values of H₂ pathways would likely remain largely unchanged because downstream costs and emissions apply to both the low/negative carbon pathways and the benchmarks.

Third, our work considered changes in GHG emissions for our fuel pathways relative to their benchmarks, but neglected changes in other environmental metrics, including air pollution, waste water, land use, and other factors. Including such factors in the analysis would provide a more holistic comparative understanding of different fuel pathways, which might be especially informative for policy-makers concerned with the full societal costs of alternative decarbonization pathways. Ogden et al estimated full societal life cycle costs of vehicular transportation, including the vehicle cost, fuel costs, externality costs for oil supply security and damage costs for greenhouse gas emissions and local criteria air pollutants [53]. They found air pollution costs accounted for 12 – 21% of the total costs for gasoline/diesel vehicles and 1% - 5% for fuel cell vehicles. If such costs were brought into our analysis, they would effectively lower the difference in LCOF between the clean and benchmark pathways and thereby reduce LCCM values.

Author contributions:

Fangwei Cheng: Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft; **Hongxi Luo:** Visualization, Writing – review & editing; **Jesse Jenkins:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition; **Eric Larson:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration

Conflicts of interest:

There are no conflicts to declare.

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APPENDIX A. Technical and cost parameters for H₂ production routes.

Table A.1 Main results. All fuel energy contents in the table and table notes are given on a higher heating value (HHV) basis, unless otherwise indicated.

	Energy conversion rate		Carbon capture rate (%)	Installed capital cost ^c (\$ ₂₀₁₆ /kW _{H2}) ^b	Fixed O&M (\$ ₂₀₁₆ /kW _{H2} -yr) ^b	Variable O&M (\$ ₂₀₁₆ /GJ _{H2}) ^b
	Main input ^a (GJ/GJ _{H2})	Co-product ^a (GJ/GJ _{H2})				
SMR ^c	1.23 (natural gas)	0	0	511	18	0.3
SMR-CCS ^d	1.26 (natural gas)	0.024 (electricity)	91.2	887	27	0
ATR-CCS ^d	1.203 (natural gas)	0.048 (electricity)	94.1	776	23	0
BGCCS-H2 ^e	1.78 (biomass)	- 0.023 (electricity)	87	2432	43	3.2
BG-H2 ^f	1.78 (biomass)	-0.079 (electricity)	0	2334	42	3.2
Electrolysis ^g	1.28 (electricity)	0	0	1332	15	0

- (a) Energy conversion rate is defined as energy input/energy output (i.e., inversion of efficiency). In the co-product column, positive values are required process inputs, and negative values are actual co-products.
- (b) All costs are expressed in 2016 \$. To convert costs from other dollar years in the original literature sources, the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index, GDP deflator, or other indices were applied.
- (c) SMR is steam-methane reforming. These estimates are directly taken from Annex A.3 of the Net-Zero America study [14, 40].
- (d) Performance and capital cost estimates for steam reforming of methane (SMR) and autothermal reforming of methane (ATR) with CO₂ capture are based on Tables 3.13, 3.8, and 3.10 in H2I NoE Report [23] for a 1.5 GW_{H2} capacity facility. The installed capital cost estimate of 721 \$₂₀₁₇/kW_{H2} for SMR-CCS and 631 \$₂₀₁₇/kW_{H2} for ATR-CCS were converted to \$ using the average \$:£ exchange rate in 2017 (1.29) and adjusting to 2016 \$. The annual fixed O&M cost is assumed to be 3% of installed capital cost. Variable operating costs are neglected.
- (e) BGCCS-H2 is hydrogen production via biomass gasification with CO₂ capture and storage. These estimates are based on Davison *et al.*'s assessment of a variety of coal-gasification based process configurations for co-production of hydrogen and electricity [31]. Values in this table are derived from Davison's cases 5.3 and 4.2. Among all of Davison's configurations, Case 5.3 produces the highest fraction of hydrogen in the outputs (97.4%), with electricity constituting the balance. Case 4.2 produces the lowest fraction (0), i.e., it produces electricity only. We assume that the ratio of performance and cost parameters between the two cases would be the same if the plants were designed for biomass instead of coal. We scale the performance and cost estimates for the 214 MW_e BGCCS-el plant described in Table A.2 using ratios of parameter values from Davison's Case 5.3 and 4.2 to estimate performance and costs for a BGCCS-H2 plant.
- Case 4.2 power output = 874.3 MW_{el}; Case 5.3 power output = 37 MW_{el}; Ratio = 874.3 / 37 = 23.6
 - Case 5.3 H₂ output / electricity output = 1,390 MW_{H2,LHV} / 37 MW_{el} = 37.6
 - The ratio of total plant cost for Case 5.3 to Case 4.2 = 2,101 M €₂₀₁₃ / 2,688 M €₂₀₁₃ = 0.78.
 - The ratio of annual fixed O&M costs for Case 5.3 to case 4.2 = 90,210,200 €₂₀₁₃ / 112,520,000 €₂₀₁₃ = 0.80.
 - The ratio of annual variable O&M costs for Case 5.3 to case 4.2 = 8,918,700 €₂₀₁₃ / 9,752,700 €₂₀₁₃ = 0.91.
 - BGCCS-H2 characteristics are, therefore:
 - Power output = BECCS-el output / (Case 4.2 / Case 5.3) = 214 MW_{el} / 23.6 = 9.06 MW_{el}
 - H₂ output = 9.06 MW_{el} * (Case 5.3 H₂/power) = 9.06 * 37.6 = 341 MW_{H2,LHV} (or 400 MW_{H2,HHV})
 - Biomass input / H₂ output = 711 MW_{bio,HHV} / 400 MW_{H2,HHV} = 1.78 MW_{bio,HHV}/MW_{H2,HHV}.
 - Electricity output / H₂ output = 9.06 / 400 = 0.023 MW_{el}/MW_{H2}.
 - The fraction of input biomass carbon captured is assumed to be 87%, the same as for a BGCCS-el facility producing electricity only (see Table A.2). This gives a CO₂ capture rate of 135 kgCO₂/GJ_{H2,HHV}.
 - Total plant cost (TPC) is estimated as the product of TPC for BGCCS-el [1,171 M \$₂₀₁₈ (see Table A.2 notes)] and the ratio of Case 5.3 to Case 4.2 TPC: 1,171 * 0.78 = 915 M \$₂₀₁₈. We add owners costs to get a total estimated installed capital cost for BGCCS-H2 of 1,083 M \$₂₀₁₈, or 2,708 \$₂₀₁₈/kW_{H2}, or 2,432 \$₂₀₁₆/kW_{H2}.
 - Annual fixed O&M is the value for BGCCS-el multiplied by the ratio of fixed O&M for Davison case 5.3 and case 4.2. Fixed O&M for BGCCS-el (from Table A.2) is 100 \$₂₀₁₆/kW-yr * 214 MW_{el} = 21.4 M \$₂₀₁₆. Thus, fixed O&M for BECCS-H2 = 21.4 M \$₂₀₁₆ * 0.80 / 400 MW_{H2,HHV} = 43 \$₂₀₁₆/kW-yr.
 - Annual variable O&M is the value for BGCCS-el multiplied by the ratio of annual O&M for Davison case 5.3 and case 4.2. Variable O&M for BGCCS-el (from Table A.2) is 23 \$₂₀₁₆/MWhr * (214 MW_{el} * 8760 * 0.9) = 39 M \$₂₀₁₆. Thus, variable O&M for BGCCS-H2 = 39 M \$₂₀₁₆ * 0.91 / (400 MW_{H2,HHV} * 8760 h/y * 0.85 CF) = 11 \$₂₀₁₆/MWh, or \$3.2/GJ_{H2}.

- (f) Parameters for BG-H2 are adapted from those for BGCCS-H2 and the coal gasification pathway (case 5.3) from Davison et al. We assume the biomass input/H₂ output ratio is the same as for BGCCS-H2. Since BG-H2 does not require CO₂ compression, the electricity output for this pathway is higher than that of BGCCS-H2. The CO₂ capture rate for BGCCS-H2 (with 87% of carbon captured) is 0.088 t CO₂/GJ_{bio}. We assume CO₂ compression requires 0.1 MWh_{el}/t CO₂, so the extra power output for BG-H2 is 711 MW_{bio} * 0.088 t CO₂/GJ_{bio} * 3.6 GJ/MWh * 0.1 MWh/t CO₂ = 22.5 MW, which corresponds to (9.06 + 22.5)/400 = 0.079 MW_{el}/MW_{H2}. The capital cost associated with CO₂ dehydration and compression is estimated to be 4% of TPC, which gives a CAPEX estimate for BG-H2 of 2,432 \$₂₀₁₆/kW_{H2} * 0.96 = 2,334 \$₂₀₁₆/kW_{H2}. FOM cost is assumed to be the same fraction of CAPEX for BG-H2 as for BGCCS H2, which corresponds to 41.5 \$/kW_{H2}. The VOM cost for BG-H2 process is assumed to be the same as for BGCCS-H2.
- (g) Parameters for electrolysis are based on a report from ENEA Consulting [33] for a PEM type electrolyzer: efficiency of 78% on HHV basis, CAPEX of 700 €₂₀₁₆/kW_{el} (896 €₂₀₁₆/kW_{H2}). Assuming a conversion rate of 1.1 \$₂₀₁₆/€₂₀₁₆ gives a CAPEX of 986 \$₂₀₁₆/kW_{H2}. FOM cost is assumed to be 1.5% of CAPEX, and VOM cost is neglected. In addition, it requires 50% of CAPEX every 40k hours of operation to replace cell stack. For 55% CF, this means stack replacement every 8 years, or 2 replacements over assumed 20-year life time. We incorporated the costs associated with replacement of stack to CAPEX, which gives \$1323/kW.

Table A.2. Supporting estimates. Performance and cost estimates for biomass-gasification-based power generation with CCS.

	Capacities		Installed capital cost (\$ ₂₀₁₆ /kW)	Fixed O&M (\$ ₂₀₁₆ /kW- y)	Variable O&M (\$ ₂₀₁₆ /MWh _{el})
	Output (MW _{el})	Input (MW _{bio})			
BGCCS-el ^a	214	711	5,811	100	23
<p>(a) The BECCS-electricity parameters are based on the case identified as SB95-B in Kreutz <i>et al.</i>[17] which includes pre-combustion CO₂ capture. In that plant design, biomass is gasified and the resulting syngas is subjected to cleaning, water gas shift, and Rectisol CO₂ removal, after which 95% of the hydrogen-rich syngas goes to fuel a gas turbine combined cycle. The remaining 5% is converted via Fischer-Tropsch synthesis to hydrocarbon liquids. The biomass input rate is 711 MW_{bio,HHV}. The net electricity output for this plant is 194.3 MW_{el}. We estimate that if 100% of the syngas were used for power generation, net electric power output would increase to 214 MW_{el} for the same biomass input level (711 MW_{bio,HHV}), and the CO₂ capture rate would be 990 kgCO₂/MWh (87% of input biomass carbon captured). Kreutz, <i>et al.</i> estimate a total plant cost (TPC) for SB95-B of 1515 M \$₂₀₁₈. Accounting for differences between the SB95-B configuration and a 100% electricity generating configuration, we estimate a TPC of 1,171 M \$₂₀₁₈ for the latter, to which we add owner's costs, resulting in a total installed capital cost of 1,386 M\$₂₀₁₈, or 5,811 \$₂₀₁₆/kW using the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index. Kreutz <i>et al.</i> indicate a 90% capacity factor for SP95-B and total annual O&M costs of 5.5% of TPC. O&M costs for the 100% electricity plant are therefore estimated to be 38 \$₂₀₁₈/MWh (= 1,171 M \$₂₀₁₈ * 0.055 / [214 * 8760 * 0.9]). We assume that non-fuel variable O&M costs are 63% of this total, based on detailed estimates for coal-gasification based electricity plant designs with CO₂ capture using GE quench gasifier [54]. Thus, variable O&M costs are 23\$₂₀₁₆/MWh and fixed operating costs are 100 \$₂₀₁₆/kW-yr.</p>					

APPENDIX B. Technical performance and cost estimates for FT and SNG production technologies.

Table B.1. Results. All fuel energy contents in the table and table notes are given on a higher heating value (HHV) basis, unless otherwise indicated.

Technology	H ₂ input GJ _{in} /GJ _{fuel,out}	Carbon input (kg CO ₂ /GJ _{fuel,out})	Installed capital cost \$ ₂₀₁₆ / kW _{fuel,out}	Fixed O&M \$ ₂₀₁₆ /kW _{fuel,out} -yr	Variable O&M \$ ₂₀₁₆ /GJ _{fuel,out}
RWGS-FTS ^a	1.47	68	952	28	0.6
Methanation ^b	1.26	50	1,650	83	0
<p>(a) This process uses reverse water-gas shift (RWGS) followed by Fischer-Tropsch synthesis (FTS) to convert input H₂ and CO₂ into refined synthetic diesel, jet fuel and LPG. The following calculations were used to estimate the H₂ input required per unit of FTL output. FTS, which synthesizes liquids from H₂ and CO, requires a fresh syngas feed of 2 kmol of H₂ for each kmol of CO. From Table 4 and Figure 12 in Greig <i>et al.</i> [29], a "once-through" FT synthesis configuration, <i>i.e.</i>, with no internal recycle of unconverted syngas or reformed light-ends, will produce 76.2 MJ/s (LHV) of liquid fuels from a fresh syngas feed containing 0.79 kg/s of H₂ (0.395 kmol/s) and 5.49 kg/s of CO (0.196 kmol/s). With internal recycle, the liquid fuels output increases 43% for the same syngas input (based on comparing outputs in Table 17 of Greig <i>et al.</i> [29], for case RC-0 and OT-0). Thus, the H₂ flow in the input syngas corresponds to 0.79 kg/s * 142 MJ_{HHV}/kgH₂ = 112 MJ_{H2,HHV}/s, or 112 / (76.2*1.43*1.05) = 0.98 MJ_{HHV} of H₂ per MJ_{HHV} of FT fuels (using HHV:LHV for FT fuels from Table 2 of this paper). Additional H₂ input is needed for the RWGS used to produce CO from CO₂. RWGS requires 1 kmol of H₂ to produce 1 kmol of CO (H₂ + CO₂ → CO + H₂O), so the overall H₂ requirement for the RWGS-FTS process is 3 kmol of H₂ for each kmol of CO₂. Thus, the total H₂ required is: (3/2)*0.98 = 1.47 MJ_{H2,HHV}/MJ_{HHV,FTL}. The installed capital cost is derived from the cost for the system design labeled RC-B in Table 17 of Greig <i>et al.</i> [29]. The FTL output capacity is the sum of liquid outputs for this design: 239 MW_{FTL,LHV} or 251 MW_{FTL,HHV}. The installed capital cost is approximated by summing the costs of two line items from Table 19 of Greig <i>et al.</i> [29], FT synthesis + refining and light ends processing, and a balance-of-plant cost estimated as the sum of line</p>					

items GT, HRSC and BOP multiplied by the fraction of syngas converted to liquids in the RC-B design. No explicit cost is included for the RWGS process, because the RC-B design in Greig *et al.* [29] includes the cost for a water gas shift reactor. This results in an estimated total capital cost for the RWGS-FTS process of 244 M\$₂₀₁₅, which converts to the unit capital cost estimate shown here. Fixed and variable O&M costs for the RWGS-FTS process is based on Capros *et al.*[34].

(b) Parameters for methanation are based on a report from ENEA consulting[33], which reports the following for a methanation isothermal reactor: efficiency of 79.4% on HHV basis, factory gate cost of 1000 €₂₀₁₆/kW_{SNG}, additional costs of 50% of the factory gate cost, and FOM cost equal to 7.5% of CAPEX. An exchange rate of 1.1 \$₂₀₁₆/€₂₀₁₆ is assumed here, and VOM cost is neglected.

APPENDIX C. Estimated leveled cost of carbon-neutral CO₂

For pathways that require an external input of carbon-neutral CO₂, we estimate the cost as the average of the cost for CO₂ capture calculated for three technologies: BGCCS-H₂, BGCCS-el, and direct air capture (DAC), plus an assumed 10 \$/tCO₂ for transport[55]. For the two biomass options, the capture costs are based on performance and cost characteristics in Appendix A, a capacity factor of 85%, and assumed revenues for H₂ and electricity of 10 \$₂₀₁₆/GJ_{H₂HHV} and 45 \$₂₀₁₆/MWh_{el}, respectively. The cost for CO₂ capture with DAC is based on the technology characteristics in Table C.1 and a capacity factor of 90%. In all cases we assume a 13% annual capital charge rate (corresponding to 0.1 WACC and 15-year economic lifetime).

With these assumptions, our estimated costs of CO₂ capture and delivery for BGCCS-H₂, BGCCS-el, and DAC are 127, 186, and 223 \$₂₀₁₆/tCO₂, respectively. These average (approximately) to 180 \$₂₀₁₆/tCO₂ (see “LCOC” tab in the Supplementary Information).

Table C.1. Technical performance and cost estimates for direct air capture system (DAC).

	Energy _{in} /Energy _{out} (all HHV basis)			
	Electricity (kWh/t CO ₂)	Installed capital cost (\$ ₂₀₁₆ /tCO ₂ /y)	Fixed O&M (\$ ₂₀₁₆ / tCO ₂ /y)	Variable OM (\$ ₂₀₁₆ / tCO ₂ /y)
DAC ^a	1824	694	27	0
(a) The DAC parameters are from Keith et al [56] (Table 2, scenario C), which reports a DAC facility that takes natural gas (5.25 GJ/t) and electricity (366 kWh/t CO ₂) as input to capture CO ₂ from atmosphere. We assume heat from natural gas can be generated using carbon neutral electricity and it yields 1824 kWh electricity to capture 1t CO ₂ from atmosphere. The capacity factor associated with DAC is assumed to be 90%.				